

Determination of Small Amounts of Praseodymium(III) and Neodymium(III) with 1-(2-Pyridylazo)-naphthol-2 in Aquo-ethanol Medium

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1-(2-Pyridylazo)-naphthol-2 has been successfully used as an amperometric reagent for the precise determination of small amounts of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} . The lower detection limit is 0.10 mg in 10 ml of the test solution of metal ion, titrations have been performed at -0.6 V vs S.C.E., $\mu=0.4$ ($\text{NH}_4\text{OH}-\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ buffer) in 80% ethanol medium. Titrations are not in any way hampered by presence of various cations and anions.

An up-to-date survey of literature reveals that no work has been done on the estimation of rare earths in alkaline range with 1-(2-pyridylazo)-naphthol-2 [PAN]. Hence, the authors have taken up the problem of determination of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} at $\text{pH}=9.0$ in 80% ethanol by amperometric titration.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalR (B.D.H.) quality. The solutions of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} were prepared and standardised¹. A 0.01M solution of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-naphthol-2 reanal grade was prepared by dissolving calculated amount of the reagent in ethanol. Its strength was checked by photometric titration².

Amperometric titrations were done on a manually operated polarograph with multiflex galvanometer (sensitivity 8.10×10^{-9} A/div) using d.m.e. as indicator and s.c.e. as reference electrodes. The d.m.e. used had capillary characteristics $m=2.373$ mg/sec and $t=3.0$ sec/drop at a mercury pressure of 41 cm.

For titrations, sets of solutions containing known amount of Pr^{III} or Nd^{III} were prepared in 80% ethanol and ionic strength for each of the test solution was adjusted to 0.4 with the requisite quantity of $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}-\text{NH}_4\text{OH}$ buffer of $\text{pH} 9.0$.

Polarography of PAN and selection of plateau potential: A C.I.C. (Baroda, India) pen recording polarograph was used to study the polarographic

behaviour of PAN. The alcoholic solution of PAN gives two stage cathodic reduction wave in ammonia buffer. A typical polarogram of 1 mM PAN in ethanol at $\mu=0.4$ (adjusted with $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}-\text{NH}_4\text{OH}$) is shown in Fig. 1. The diffusion current is proportional to the concentration of PAN. The plateau potential, i.e. -0.6 V vs S.C.E. was fixed on manually operated polarograph for the amperometric titrations of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} as they do not give any diffusion current at that potential.

Fig. 1. Polarogram of 1 mM PAN in ammonia buffer $\text{pH}=9.0$, $\mu=0.4$ and medium 80% ethanol.

TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC TITRATION OF Pr^{III} AND Nd^{III} WITH PAN IN 80% ETHANOL MEDIUM
 Plateau Potential = -0.6 vs S.C.E., pH = 9.0, $\mu = 0.4$

Sl. no.	Approximate molarity $\times 10^{-4}$	Amount of Pr ^{III}			Amount of Nd ^{III}		
		taken mg	found mg	Std. dev.*	taken mg	found mg	Std. dev.*
1.	0.7	0.0989	0.0976	0.0006	0.1009	0.1002	0.0005
2.	0.8	0.1127	0.1118	0.0007	0.1153	0.1158	0.0006
3.	1	0.1409	0.1416	0.0009	0.1412	0.1454	0.0008
4.	2	0.2818	0.2806	0.0018	0.2884	0.2862	0.0017
5.	4	0.5636	0.5652	0.0032	0.5768	0.5784	0.0022
6.	6	0.8454	0.8430	0.0058	0.8652	0.8604	0.0028
7.	8	1.1272	1.1228	0.0091	1.1536	1.1502	0.0038
8.	10	1.4091	1.4032	0.0121	1.4424	1.4495	0.0056
9.	20	2.8182	2.8276	0.0178	2.8848	2.8898	0.0108
10.	30	4.2273	4.2455	0.0216	4.3272	4.3157	0.0236

*Values calculated from five titrations for each concentration.

Results and Discussion

For titrations, each of the test solutions was taken into a titration cell and the standard solution of PAN was added dropwise from semimicro burette, when a yellowish red colouration was observed. The current was noted with multiflex galvanometer. On plotting galvanometer reading after necessary volume correction⁶, against the volume of PAN, reversed L-shaped curves were obtained (Fig. 2). The end point indicates metal :

Fig. 2. Amperometric titration curves of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} with PAN at pH 9.0 in aquo-ethanol medium. P = 0.0015 mM of Pr^{III} titrated against 0.005 mM/ml PAN, N = 0.001 mM of Nd^{III} titrated against 0.0025 mM/ml PAN.

PAN ratio of 1 : 3 which is in good agreement with the literature^{4,5}. For each concentration five

titrations were performed and the mean values are reported in Table 1. The coefficient of variation never exceeded (0.86) and this indicates the high accuracy of the method. The results are reproducible and the lowest detectable limits are 0.0986 mg for Pr^{III} and 0.1009 mg for Nd^{III} in 10 ml solution. The statistical data and lowest detection limits reveal the sensitivity of this reagent over others, viz. xylenol orange⁶, methyl thymol blue⁷ and alizarin red-S⁸.

Tolerance limits : To study the tolerance limits of the method employed, known amount of foreign metal ions were added to a definite amount of metal (Pr^{III} or Nd^{III}) and the solution was titrated following the procedure as described above. Titrations of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} are not in any way hampered by the presence of cations like Be^{II} (4.5 mg), Tl^I (10.2 mg), Pb^{II} (10.4 mg), Mg^{II} (24.4 mg), Cd^{II} (30.0 mg), Cr^{III} (39.0 mg), Li (52.0 mg), Na (80.5 mg) and K (97.5 mg). Moreover, fairly large amounts of anions like Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻, SO₄²⁻, CH₃COO⁻ and C₂O₄²⁻ have no effect on these amperometric titrations.

References

1. S. C. LAVALE and K. S. PITRE, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1981, 30, 328.
2. B. F. PEASE and M. B. WILLIAMS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, 31, 1044.
3. J. T. STOCK, "Amperometric Titration", R. E. KRIEGER, Huntington, New York, 1957, pp. 7-8.
4. C. T. HSU, L. A. LING and Y. S. ING, *Hua Hsueh*, 1971, 1, 111.
5. I. M. RAO, D. SATYANARAYANA and U. AGARWALA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1979, 52, 588.
6. S. C. LAVALE and K. S. PITRE, *Madhya Bharati, J. Saugar Univ.*, 1980, 28, 49.
7. S. C. LAVALE and K. S. PITRE, *Anal. Chem.*, 1982, 6, 170.
8. S. C. LAVALE and K. S. PITRE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1982, 55, 2232.